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Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation Of Herbal Anti-Acne Face Wash

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ABSTRACT

The use of herbal face washes to remove extra oil from the skin and replenish it with natural nutrients has made them more and more popular as a means of treating acne and pimples. Strong plant-based components found in these products often include neem (*Azadirachta indica*) and feverfew (*Tanacetum parthenium*). Many herbal medicines are based on herbal formulations, which can be found in a variety of forms including tinctures, powdered herbs, extracts, and oils made from plants. Herbal products are becoming more and more popular worldwide. The creation of a herbal face wash with aqueous extracts of orange peel, tulsi leaf, and neem leaf is one noteworthy project in this discipline. After a thorough evaluation of variables like color, pH, consistency, washability, irritation, and spreadability, the study showed that this herbal face wash performed better than commercial options. Since every ingredient in this composition is herbal, it is thought to be dependable and safe for use in skincare products.

INTRODUCTION

Inflammation in hair follicles causes acne, which manifests as a variety of skin imperfections, including blackheads, whiteheads, and pimples. Hormonal fluctuations, germs, dead skin cell accumulation, and excessive oil production are some of the common causes. Acne is typically linked to puberty; however, it can affect people of any age. Treatment options include oral or topical drugs, lifestyle changes, and the adoption of excellent skincare habits. A dermatologist can provide customized guidance for the best results. Increased oil production, bacterial

development, hormonal changes, and inflammation are the main reasons of acne, which usually affects the face, chest, shoulders, and back. It can range in intensity from moderate, with a few blemishes, to severe, with painful and widespread eruptions. Changing one's lifestyle, following recommended skincare practices, and occasionally turning to medicine are all necessary for managing and treating acne. Herbal face wash, made with plant-based components instead of harsh chemicals and artificial additions, provide a gentler cleansing choice. Aloe vera, tea tree oil, chamomile, and neem are a few examples of the

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calming, anti-inflammatory, and antibacterial ingredients they frequently include. Herbal face washes are popular among people looking for natural and possibly less harsh cleaning solutions. The choice of wash should be made depending on the skin type and its sensitivity. Moreover, herbal face wash includes antioxidant and anti-inflammatory qualities that help with skin conditions like acne, redness, and inflammation. Their goal is to nourish and renew the skin through the use of herbal components, resulting in a complexion that is healthier and more beautiful. Many people choose to cleanse their faces with herbal face washes, which preserve the skin's natural oils and promote the health of their skin at its best. For optimal effects, choose a herbal face wash based on your unique skin type and preferences.

ACNE

Under the skin's surface, clogged hair follicles cause the widespread skin ailment known as acne. Sebum oil, which keeps the skin from drying out, and dead skin cells clog the pores, causing lesions often known as zits or pimples. Although the face is the most commonly affected location, the back, chest, and shoulders can also have outbreaks. The sebaceous (oil) glands, which are attached to hair follicles that contain fine hairs, become irritated and cause acne. Sebum, which is secreted onto the skin's surface through microscopic pores in the follicles, is produced by these glands in healthy skin. Keratinocytes are a kind of skin cell that lines the follicles. As the body sheds skin cells, keratinocytes normally migrate to the surface of the skin. But in the case of acne, sebum, hair, and keratinocytes build up inside the pore, obstructing sebum from penetrating the skin's surface and inhibiting keratinocyte shedding. Bacteria that often live on the skin are attracted to this buildup, which causes swelling, redness, heat, and pain. Lesions or pimples form when the wall of the

clogged follicle bursts, releasing bacteria, skin cells, and oil into the surrounding skin.

TYPES OF ACNE

Acne can present as a variety of lesions, most frequently known as pimples. Medical professionals classify things according to their attributes. Among the varieties of acne are:

- **Whiteheads:**

A white lump that remains beneath the skin's surface due to clogged hair follicles.

- **Blackheads:**

Clogged follicles that break open once they reach the skin's surface. Not dirt, but air exposure discolouring stored sebum is why they appear black.

- **Papules:**

Inflammatory lesions that generally appear as little, pink skin lumps that are touch-sensitive. Pustules, often known as pimples: Papules topped with lesions filled with white or yellow pus that are frequently red at the base.

- **Nodules:**

large, painful, solid lesions that are firmly ingrained in the skin.

- **Severe nodular acne:**

also referred to as cystic acne: this kind is characterized by painful, deep, pus-filled lesions.

HERBAL FACE WASH

Herbal face wash uses the inherent power of plants to naturally cleanse and renew your skin, making them a mild and refreshing substitute for conventional face washes. These face wash efficiently eliminate pollutants and superfluous oil while providing a calming and revitalizing feeling thanks to the infusion of botanical extracts and essential oils.

The main advantages are as follows:

- **Gentle Cleansing:**

Natural oils in the skin are preserved and made acceptable for all skin types, especially sensitive skin, by the use of herbal components such as aloe vera, chamomile, and green tea.

- **Natural Hydration:**

After washing, ingredients like cucumber and honey help to moisturize and hydrate the skin, leaving it feeling silky and supple.

- **Anti-inflammatory Properties:**

Herbs with anti-inflammatory properties, like lavender and calendula, soothe sensitive skin by reducing redness and irritation.

- **Antioxidant Protection:**

A lot of herbal extracts have antioxidants in them that protect the skin from environmental damage brought on by free radicals, which helps to keep the skin looking healthy and glowing.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

MATERIAL:

Sr. No.	INGREDIENTS	PROPERTIES	USES
1.	<p>NEEM (Azadirachta indica)</p>	<p>Neem has antimicrobial, antiviral, antifungal, antioxidant, antidiabetic and anti-inflammatory properties.</p>	<p>Neem has antibacterial qualities that help control and reduce the microorganisms that cause breakouts of acne.</p>
2.	<p>TULSI (Ocimum tenuiflorum)</p>	<p>Tulsi has antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, immunomodulatory, antidiabetic and anti-cancer properties.</p>	<p>Tulsi's antibacterial and healing properties helps in combating acne and other skin problems.</p>
3.	<p>ROSEMARY (Salvia rosmarinus)</p>	<p>Rosemary possesses anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties. It is also rich in antioxidants.</p>	<p>Rosemary plant extract not only reduce the inflammation associated with acne but also fights with bacteria that causes acne outbreaks.</p>
4.	<p>ALOE VERA (Aloe barbadensis)</p>	<p>Aloe vera has antibacterial, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties.</p>	<p>Due to its antibacterial properties' aloe vera is very beneficial to control and reduce acne causing bacteria.</p>

5.	<p>LEMON (<i>Citrus limon</i>)</p>	<p>Lemon has antibacterial, immunostimulant and anti-inflammatory properties. It also has antioxidant properties.</p>	<p>Citric acid in lemon can fade blemishes and even out your skin tone. It is also an effective way of reducing excess oil and sebum which in turn prevents acne.</p>
6.	<p>HONEY</p>	<p>Honey possesses antimicrobial, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties.</p>	<p>Because of its antimicrobial and restorative qualities, honey is a useful natural acne treatment. It can lessen the frequency of pimples and enhance their appearance.</p>
7.	<p>XANTHAN GUM</p>	<p>Xanthan gum has thickening, stabilizing, suspending and gelling properties.</p>	<p>Xanthan gum is frequently used in skin care products as a thickener and stabiliser. It is also recognized for its moisturising qualities.</p>
8.	<p>ROSE WATER</p>	<p>Rose water has anti-inflammatory, hydrating, antibacterial and anti-aging properties.</p>	<p>Rose water is a natural toner that shrinks acne lesions, clears the pores, and gets rid of extra oil. It helps get rid of microorganisms that cause acne and stops breakouts from happening again.</p>

METHOD:

Soxhlet extraction method:

- To start, add the recommended amount of xanthan gum to some warm rose water, then let it soak for the entire night.

- After that, add enough honey, a few squeezes of lemon juice, glycerin, and fresh aloe vera to the blend.
- Next, add as much herbal extract as you would like, then enough soap, and blend until well combined.

Composition table of Herbal Face Wash:

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Quantity Taken
1	Neem extract	1 ml
2	Tulsi extract	1 ml
3	Rosemary extract	2 ml
4	Xanthan Gum	2 gm
5	Aloe Vera	2 ml
6	Honey	1 ml
7	Lemon Juice	1 ml
8	Rosewater	q.s

EVALUATION PARAMETER**1. Physical Evaluation**

The physical assessment includes the following examinations:

- Color
- Odor
- Consistency

2. Washability

The herbal face wash is applied to the face and then promptly rinsed off with water, followed by personal examination.

3. pH test

Use a pH meter to find the herbal face wash's pH by doing the following steps:

- Turn the pH meter's digital on.
- Use standard water to calibrate the meter.
- Measure the pH of a 1% aqueous solution of the formulation using the calibrated digital pH meter, making sure the temperature stays constant.

4. Irritancy Test

To make sure skincare products don't create negative responses, irritability testing are essential. The left hand's dorsal surface receives a square centimeter of the face wash in this test, which is then left for one to two hours to be monitored.

5. Grittiness Test

The grittiness test determines if there are any gritty particles present in the formulation. Application of the herbal face wash to the skin is conducted to

check for the presence of gritty particles, with results indicating the absence of any.

6. Foaming Test

A tiny amount of the prepared herbal face wash is applied to the face in the foaming test to gauge how well it foams. After then, the application is left to interact with water to watch foam development.

7. Spreadability

By sandwiching about 500 mg of the cream between two slides, spreadability is evaluated. The upper slide is fastened with a non-flexible rope, excess formulation is adjusted, and the top slide is weighted with a 100g load. Concurrently, the lower slide is fastened to the apparatus's board and filled with 20g of weight. Next, the duration of time required for the upper slide to slide off is recorded.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The prepared formulations underwent satisfactory results tests for color, smell, consistency, pH, spreadability, washability, grittiness, irritancy, viscosity.

Physical examination of formulation:

Sr. No.	Physical Parameters	Result
1	Color	Yellowish-white
2	Odor	Pleasant
3	Appearance	Translucent
4	Consistency	Semi-solid

Evaluation of formulation:

Sr. No.	Evaluation Parameter	Result
1	Washability	Good
2	Irritancy	Non-irritant
3	Grittiness	Non-gritty
4	pH	5.9
5	Spreadability (gm-cm/sec)	5.416

DISCUSSION

Plants provide an abundance of nutrients that can improve one's health, including vitamins, antioxidants, oils, essential oils, proteins, and much more. Face wash solutions are unique among the variety of herbal remedies used to prevent acne

since they may both cleanse and moisturize the face. These tailored face wash provide vital nutrients to support skin health and enhance its inherent brightness, making them suitable for a variety of skin types. The method for creating these products is outlined in this research, which makes use of plant extracts including neem, tulsi, lemon, honey, and the calming ingredient xanthan gum that are well-known for their ability to nourish skin. Extensive examinations were carried out concerning multiple factors, including colour, pH, texture, risibility, possibility for irritation, and spreadability. The results show that the herbal face wash formulation outperforms products that are sold in stores, providing better effectiveness because of its herbal makeup, which is considered safe and reliable for skincare.

CONCLUSION

Herbal face wash formulations were developed and assessed for this study, with an emphasis on physicochemical properties including color, scent, taste, pH level, spreadability, grittiness, consistency, and washability. Herbal components like tulsi, rosemary, aloe vera, lemon juice, rose water, and neem, which is well-known for its antibacterial and analgesic qualities were included in the formulations. According to evaluation results, all parameters colour, fragrance, texture, pH balance, spreadability, risibility, and grittiness were performed satisfactorily. The results indicate that the herbal face wash formulation is more effective than commercially available alternatives. Because every ingredient in this composition is herbal, it is considered safe and reliable for skincare.

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